

BIM EXECUTION PLAN (BEP)

The Project **Urban PERISCOPE** INTEGRATED/0918/0034 is co-financed by the European Regional Development Fund and the Republic of Cyprus through the Research Innovation Foundation.

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Abstract

The scope of the BIM Execution Plan is to outline the way the Urban PERISCOPE project team will use BIM workflows, tools, and methodologies to achieve the desired project outcomes. It includes details such as the roles and responsibilities of the stakeholders that will be involved, the timeline for the project, the methods that the team should follow as well as the deliverables that should be produced. It also includes information about the BIM quality management system to be used and the software and hardware that will be required. In short, the present document sets the goals and coordinates of the project and communicates the BIM goals and objectives.

This guideline document is based on a standard Exchange Information Requirements (EIR) Template based on ISO 19650-1, which is required for service agreements or contracts following CIC BIM Standards.

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Index

1. INTRODUCTION	7
1.1. Document Purpose.....	7
1.2. Applied BIM Standards.....	7
1.3. Definition.....	8
2. Project Information	10
2.1. Scope of work.....	10
2.2. Project Team Organization.....	11
2.3. Project Milestones	12
3. BIM Methodologies	13
3.1. Scan to HBIM.....	13
3.2. BIM Implementation	16
3.3. BIM Modeling Strategy	21
4. Information Delivery Plan	22
4.2. Model QA/QC	23
5. Planning and Documentation	25
5.1. LOD Requirements	25
5.2. Collaboration - CDE	25
6. Standard Methods and Procedure	25
6.1. Folder Structure	25
6.2. Document Name Convention	25
6.3. Model Name Convention	25

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Introduction

1.1 Document Purpose

This document provides all the necessary information for the development of a digital twin model using the Heritage Building Information Modelling (HBIM) process, within the Urban Periscope project. In line with the definition of ISO 19650, the BEP specifies the management, technical and project information and deliverables required for the project in a way that is specific, measurable, achievable, and realistic.

All stakeholders must adhere to and follow the BEP.

The project BEP shall accompany the documents that inform the stakeholders about decisions in the existing conditions survey, the Non – Destructive Techniques methodology (NDT), the BIM modelling, the BIM implementation method and the deliverables related to the digital asset under study.

In detail,

- To define the Organization of the Team that is responsible for the implementation of Scan- to- to-HBIM process.
- To describe applicable workflows and procedures for each methodology of Scan-to-HBIM.
- To define the applicable BIM Standards.
- To identify the deliverables of HBIM.
- To identify the project milestones relevant to the HBIM process.
- To define the overall communication and collaboration protocols.
- To identify the applicable LOD.

1.2 Applied BIM Standards

The purpose of this section is to define the BIM standards, Guidance, Classification and Specifications that will be applied through the UP Project. All Project stakeholders must confirm compliance and demonstrate understanding of these standards; BIM will be aligned with the UK Government BIM Level 2 British Standards Institution (BS 1192:2007+A2:2016), Publicly Available Specifications (PAS 1192-2:2013), ISO standards (BS EN ISO 16950-1&2) and CSI MasterFormat 2014- this should be understood by the BIM team and other stakeholders.

1.3 Definitions

AEG

Architecture, Engineering and Construction.

Asset

Item, thing, or entity that has potential or actual value to an organization.

BEP

BIM Execution Plan. A plan that explains how the information management aspects of the appointment will be carried out by the delivery team.

BIM

Building Information Model / Modelling. Use of a shared digital representation of a built asset to facilitate construction, operation design, and processes to form a reliable basis for decisions.

HBIM

Heritage Building Information modeling (HBIM) can be defined as a semantic-aware database of historical buildings, in which the geometric model is connected to descriptive multi-source information. It consists of a useful tool in the historical documentation (e.g., phasing) and conservation (e.g., state analysis) of built structures.

Scan to BIM

The capture of the space, and turning it into a digital model that can be used for planning, monitoring or managing the built environment and communicating and sharing project information with stakeholders.

BS

Building Smart, (International Industry body)

BOQ

Bill of quantities

CDE

Common Data Environments

CIM

City Information Modelling

CoBie

Construction Operations Building Information Exchange. The international standard for information exchange about construction, data is focused from a BIM methodology point of view.

DES

Data Exchange Schemas

Digital Twin

A digital twin is a virtual parametric model designed to accurately represent a physical object.

IFC

Industry Foundation Class (Digital file format)

ISO

International Organization for Standardization

LCA

Life Cycle Analysis

LOD

Level of Development. It defines the level of Information contained in a BIM model.

MEP

Mechanical, Electrical and Plumbing

MVD

Model View Definition

Point Cloud

The result of a data collection of a building or object by a laser scanner or photogrammetry, consisting of a set of points in the space that reflect its surface.

NDT

Non-Destructive Techniques

Space

A space is defined as a building volume enclosed by ceilings, floors, walls, or another space's boundary. Space has a plethora of properties assigned to it to describe its energy resources, such as loads from people, lighting, and equipment.

MF

Model federation Creation of a composite information model from separate models. An assembly of distinct models to create a single, complete building information model of an asset.

OmniClass

The OmniClass Construction Classification System, also known as OmniClass™ or OCCS, is a classification system used for the organising and retrieving of information for the construction industry. For more information, see <https://www.csiresources.org/standards/omniclass>.

Model- Digital representation of part of the physical and/or functional characteristics of the Project.

Project- means the project to which the EIR relates.

Project Information

The project “Portal for heritage buildings integration into the contemporary built environment” (Urban PERIsCOPE- UP) aims to design and develop an innovative platform for the identification, classification, documentation, and renovation of heritage buildings which can be exploited by a variety of stakeholders related to the conservation and retrofit activities. UP will enable the exploitation of state-of-the-art techniques in the scientific fields of Building Information Modelling (BIM), remote sensing, terrestrial and aerial 3D modelling techniques, and non-destructive onsite testing, pursued by the leading research and academic institutions of Cyprus in these fields. UP platform is targeted to specific stakeholders to impact culturally and economically the society of Cyprus, including public authorities and policymakers (Town Planning and Housing Department, Department of Antiquities, Municipalities) and professionals (archaeologists, engineers, architects, and chartered surveyors).

The implementation of UP in practice involves the pilot application of the proposed holistic integrated methodology on 18 heritage buildings in Nicosia and Limassol (including examples located in both Greek Cypriot and Turkish Cypriot neighbourhoods), with regards to their location in the contemporary fabric of the city, as well as their current structural condition. This pilot application will enable the generation of an integrated database, from which information and data will be extracted, to be used for the development of the methodology with feedback collected from the stakeholders engaged in the project. The development of the platform and associated tools will bring added value and benefits to the Public Authorities and Cultural Operators participating and to the Consortium as a whole.

UP methodology will approach the challenges and identified issues of heritage buildings from multiple points of view, including (i) the mapping and parametric management of data of heritage buildings through BIM, (ii) the documentation of architectural typology and architectonic features, (iii) the method of construction, (iv) the definition of their structural condition, and (v) the restoration and renovation requirements. The platform will be used for the monitoring of urban growth and the evaluation of urban plans by authorities, the documentation and valuation of heritage buildings and the update of existing catalogues, and an introduction of incentives required for the buildings’ structural and energy retrofitting.

2.1. Scope of work

The scope of this document is to describe in detail the multiple phases required in order to optimize and create a hierarchy of the data collected (i.e., metadata linked with 3D assets), such as existing conditions information, conservation state analysis, existing conditions survey as well as diverse forms of geometric characterization (patterns, geometric rules, or curve generation) and ways of archiving data such as old drawings folders, or as-built models. The proposed strategy intends to ensure the creation of a digitised information management process that all stakeholders should follow to maintain consistency and facilitate collaborative working.

2.2 Project team organization

The purpose of this section is to stipulate the allocation of roles and responsibilities associated with the management of the model and project information.

The Consultant indicates the Project Team Members carrying the following roles, indicating their capability and experience to fulfil the requirements of the roles. The same person can fulfil different roles:

Figure 1 – Project Team Organization Chart.

2.3 Project Milestones

The proposed strategy intends to ensure the creation of a digital information management process that all stakeholders should follow to maintain consistency and facilitate collaborative work. In detail, the data integrated into the BIM models is related to the 3D geometrical Survey of case study buildings, the NDT and the Modeling Historical Building Sustainability Aspects – LCA. On the other way, the BIM team exports the open-source file in *ifc file format and deliver it to the team who conducts the LCA analysis. Moreover, the UP BIM team exports and delivers the properly organised (based on the BIM data delivered diagram) HBIM Data to be uploaded to the BIM Platform.

Figure 2 – HBIM data received and delivered diagram.

BIM Methodologies

3.1 Scan-to-Hbim

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Scan to h-BIM

* The document under the title Naming Convention and File Structure: NameConvention applies to all phases of the Scan to BIM

3.2 BIM Implementation

The BIM Implementation methodology starts with the stage of the collection and integration of all the historical data related to the case study building such as images, drawings, descriptions of the current conditions, publications, and interviews. The UP team shall fill in all the templates that create of a central file with all the necessary information. This file will prove a useful tool for the management of the historical heritage data related to the selected cultural heritage buildings. Furthermore, it provides the documentary basis for the analysis and development of the preservation of cultural heritage buildings.

Moreover, the conservation state analysis involves in-situ measurements as well as the development of all necessary processes to draw the appropriate conclusions about the state of deterioration of the buildings. While more information concerning the structural aspects of the investigated buildings should be delivered in datasets related to NDT activities, which must be integrated into the BIM models and the HBIM platform. On-site visits and in-situ measurements for the definition of the structural condition and selected thermal properties of building elements – as described in Exchange Information Requirements for LCA and NDT – must be implemented as well. During the on-site visits, the documentation of the building materials used in each building element of the investigated building should be implemented. Non-destructive testing (NDT) with the use of IR thermography should also be implemented, to identify structural failures which were not optically identified. The environmental conditions during the measurement, as well as information affecting the NDT measurements, must also be documented - *Figure 7 – BIM Implementation Diagram*

Information Requirements for BIM

Existing Conditions Information

Conservation State Analysis

Existing Conditions Survey

Drawings

Building's Identity Data

Photographs

Photographs

Report

Reality Capture TLS & Photogrammetry

Non Destructive Technique

Identity Data Report

Parcel	131
Building Name	STR_131
Listing Status	listed
Sheet	21
Drawing	61E1
Parcel	131
Plot Number	131
Condition	Conserved
Occupation Status	occupied
Current Use	residential
Original Use	residential
Entrance	
Orientation	north-east
Accessibility	accessible
Zone	Ka4a
Development Plan	Nicosia Local Plan

Listed Tab

Description

IM_476
Address: 16a Jorjias 11 & Drossinos Solomou

The building is located on a corner plot opposite the Central Police Station of Lemesos and next to the Water Tower, which was constructed in 1930 and is considered a symbol of the city and a monument of engineering. The building itself existed, at some form, before 1951. At that year, a number of additions and alterations were made so that two individual buildings were created in the plot, both used as houses.

The single-storey house of 1953 consisted of a central hall, a dining room, a corridor, two bedrooms, a kitchen, a bathroom, a toilet, a covered veranda, an uncovered veranda and a cellar, presumably at the semi-underground room at the back of the house.

In 1959, a window at the main north facade of the building was transformed into a door as part of the transformation of a room to a shop.

During the 90s, a group of companies bought the plot with the intention of demolishing the two houses and erect a four-storey building with shops and offices. The development was blocked by the Municipality, mainly because of its proximity to the Water Tower. The second house that existed in the plot was eventually demolished sometime after 1998. At the time of its demolition, it was abandoned and in very bad condition. In the area it previously occupied, there is a parking lot today.

In 2000 the Municipality acquired the building so that a museum dedicated to the nearby Water Tower is developed. This development was never implemented due to various reasons. Before the acquisition, the building was included in the catalogue of listed buildings in 2003, as a building of urban vernacular architecture with modernist neoclassical elements.

The walls, floors, frames and roof of the building follow the trends of its time. The external walls are made of stonework, covered with plaster. The floor of the central room and, partly, the front veranda is made of painted tiles while the rest of the rooms have wooden plank floors. All doors and windows, as well as their frames, are made of wood. The roof consists of timber beams and tiles.

Geometric survey objectives

[Complete the chart below, adding items as needed. You may also wish to remove or shorten the table]

UML # Class	Element	Typical Exterior Space		Typical Interior Space		Typical As-Built Scan / Model	
		Scan	Model	Scan	Model	Scan	Model
A1010	Standard Foundations						
A1020	Special Foundations						
A1030	Slab on Grade						
A2010	Basement Excavation						
A2020	Basement Walls						
B1010	Floor Construction						
B1020	Roof Construction						
B2010	Exterior Walls						
B2020	Exterior Windows						
B2030	Exterior Doors						
B3010	Roof Ceilings						
B3020	Roof Ceilings						
C1010	Partitions						
C1020	Interior Doors						
C1030	Fittings						
C2010	Stair Construction						
C2020	Stair Finishes						
C3010	Wall Finishes						
C3020	Floor Finishes						

Exchange Information Requirements for Geometrical Data Survey

&

Technical specifications for the geometric survey and general conservation state visual analysis

EIR for NDT

Methods

Activities

Steps

Templates & Reports

Results

Documents

Methods

Activities

Steps

Templates & Reports

Results

Documents

Determination of Data Quality

Data Acquisition

Data Curation

Reality Capture TLS & Photogrammetry

Report

Project Planning

Appendix 1- Project Planning Template

PP1. Geometrical Data Survey Information
[add specific information on the case study building]

PP1.1 Building Information
 Identification number: *[add specific information on the case study building]*
 Building Name: *[add specific information on the case study building]*
 Building Location: *[add specific information on the case study building]*
 Building Address: *[add specific information on the case study building]*
 Building Type/Use: *[add specific information on the case study building]*
 Number of floors: *[add specific information on the case study building]*
 Height of the building: *[add specific information on the case study building]*
 Levels Above Grade: *[add specific information on the case study building]*
 Levels Below Grade: *[add specific information on the case study building]*
 Square Footage of Building: *[add specific information on the case study building]*
 Phases (construction / modification): *[add specific information on the case study building]*
 Name & Address of owner: *[add specific information on the case study building]*

PP1.2 Existing Documentation
 Indicate what documentation is available and what file formats
 Floor Plans (PDF or CAD?): *[add specific information on the case study building]*
 Elevations (PDF or CAD?): *[add specific information on the case study building]*
 Site Plan (PDF or CAD?): *[add specific information on the case study building]*
 Photographs: *[add specific information on the case study building]*
 Other: *[add specific information on the case study building]*

PP1.3 Accessibility and Field Conditions
 Protection information: *[add specific information on the case study building]*
 Protection date: *[add specific information on the case study building]*
 Occupied or Vacant? *[add specific information on the case study building]*
 Is power available? *[add specific information on the case study building]*
 Hazardous Conditions: *[add specific information on the case study building]*

PP2. Project Objectives
 PP2. 1 Statement of Intent
[add specific information on the case study building]

PP2. 2 Level of Accuracy
[add specific information on the case study building]

Data Acquisition

Appendix 2- Data Acquisition Report

DA1 Survey Instrument Calibration
[add specific information on the case study building]

DA2 Survey Control
[add specific information on the case study building]

DA3 Survey plan
[add specific information on the case study building]

DA3.1 Site Conditions
[add specific information on the case study building]

DA3.2 Location of geometric survey equipment
[add specific information on the case study building]
 Useful Range
[add specific information on the case study building]
 Point Density
[add specific information on the case study building]
 Positioning
[add specific information on the case study building]

DA3.3 Targets
[add specific information on the case study building]

DA3.4 Color checker
[add specific information on the case study building]

DA3.5 Scale metric
[add specific information on the case study building]

DA3.4 Detailed textures
[add specific information on the case study building]

Data Processing

Appendix 3- Data Processing Template

DP1 Registration Accuracy
 Building Name and location: *[add specific information on the case study building]*
 Date: *[add specific information on the case study building]*
 Author of report: *[add specific information on the case study building]*
 Describe the method use to perform the registration: *[add specific information on the case study building]*
 Registration results: *[add specific information on the case study building]*
 Does the registration fall within the range of acceptable error?
[add specific information on the case study building]

DP2 Visual Data Check Report
 Describe the method use to perform the visual data check
[add specific information on the case study building]
 Visual data check results: *[add specific information on the case study building]*
 Corrective action taken (if any): *[add specific information on the case study building]*

DP3 Model Check
[add specific information on the case study building]

DP3.1 Model integrity
 Provide information that there are no undefined elements
[add specific information on the case study building]
 Provide information that there are no incorrectly defined elements
[add specific information on the case study building]
 Provide information that there are no duplicated elements
[add specific information on the case study building]
 Provide information that elements are right fitting or "water tight"
[add specific information on the case study building]
 Describe methods used to perform the model integrity checks
[add specific information on the case study building]
 Present model integrity results: *[add specific information on the case study building]*
 Corrective action taken (if any): *[add specific information on the case study building]*

DP3.2 Model control checks
 Provide information that that model coordinates match the acquired data coordinates
[add specific information on the case study building]
 Provide information that of inclusion and proper alignment of the control points in the model
[add specific information on the case study building]
 Describe method use to perform the model control checks
[add specific information on the case study building]
 Present model control checks results: *[add specific information on the case study building]*
 Corrective action taken: *[add specific information on the case study building]*
 Name of the individual who performed the model control checks
[add specific information on the case study building]

Project Data Deliverable

Appendix 4: Project Data Deliverable Report

PDD1. Project Delivery Approach
[Provide a summary explanation of overall sequencing of how the project and the required 3D imaging effort are broken down into various parts, if applicable. Explain how the 3D imaging efforts will integrate into the larger design project and the expectation for support after the initial data is collected.]

PDD2. Input Data
 PDD2.1 Laser Scanner point cloud
 Scans quality
[add specific information on the case study building]

Number of inputs
[add specific information on the case study building]

Type and number markers
 Number of control markers: *[add specific information on the case study building]*
 Number of test markers: *[add specific information on the case study building]*

Point cloud color mode
 Colorized

Point cloud density
[add specific information on the case study building]

Point cloud coordinate system
 Aligned with the coordinate system

Modified point cloud data
 Alignment
 Cleaning
 Density reduction
 Other *[add specific information on the case study building]*

Point cloud output format
 *e57
 *las or *laz
 *ply

Exchange Information Requirements for Geometrical Data Survey

&

Technical specifications for the geometric survey and
 general conservation state visual analysis tender

BIM Modeling

Methods

Activities

Steps

Results

Documents

Geometrical Survey

Family Generation

Material Composition

Structural and thermal condition integration with NDT

Historical Data Integration

3D model

BIM Library

BIM Material

3D model

Parameter

EIR for BIM

*rte- Architectural Revit Template

EIR for NDT

BIM Implementation

Methods

Results

***ifc**
Open-Source file

2D
Drawings

3D
Model

4D
Phasing & Typology

5D
BOQ

6D
LCA

h-BIM
Digital twin

Material Name	Type	Material	Material
Instance	Area	Volume	
CH_ARC_CementPlaster	CY_ARC_12 m ²	0.32 m ³	
CH_ARC_CementPlaster	CY_ARC_13 m ²	0.50 m ³	
CH_ARC_GypsumPlaster	CY_ARC_12 m ²	0.18 m ³	
CH_ARC_GypsumPlaster	CY_ARC_13 m ²	0.19 m ³	
CH_ARC_GypsumPlaster	CY_ARC_12 m ²	0.18 m ³	
CH_ARC_GypsumPlaster	CY_ARC_14 m ²	0.21 m ³	
CH_ARC_GypsumPlaster	CY_ARC_12 m ²	0.18 m ³	
CH_ARC_GypsumPlaster	CY_ARC_13 m ²	0.20 m ³	
CH_ARC_GypsumPlaster	CY_ARC_14 m ²	0.12 m ³	
CH_ARC_GypsumPlaster	CY_ARC_14 m ²	0.21 m ³	
CH_ARC_GypsumPlaster	CY_ARC_12 m ²	0.10 m ³	
CH_ARC_GypsumPlaster	CY_ARC_13 m ²	0.14 m ³	
CH_ARC_GypsumPlaster	CY_ARC_13 m ²	0.14 m ³	
CH_ARC_GypsumPlaster	CY_ARC_19 m ²	0.14 m ³	
CH_ARC_GypsumPlaster	CY_ARC_13 m ²	0.15 m ³	
CH_ARC_GypsumPlaster	CY_ARC_17 m ²	0.10 m ³	
CH_ARC_GypsumPlaster	CY_ARC_13 m ²	0.16 m ³	
CH_ARC_GypsumPlaster	CY_ARC_18 m ²	0.12 m ³	
CH_ARC_GypsumPlaster	CY_ARC_12 m ²	0.18 m ³	
CH_ARC_GypsumPlaster	CY_ARC_18 m ²	0.12 m ³	
CH_ARC_GypsumPlaster	CY_ARC_18 m ²	0.12 m ³	
CH_ARC_GypsumPlaster	CY_ARC_19 m ²	0.14 m ³	
CH_ARC_GypsumPlaster	CY_ARC_12 m ²	0.18 m ³	
CH_ARC_GypsumPlaster	CY_ARC_18 m ²	0.12 m ³	
CH_ARC_GypsumPlaster	CY_ARC_19 m ²	0.14 m ³	
CH_ARC_GypsumPlaster	CY_ARC_13 m ²	0.19 m ³	
CH_ARC_GypsumPlaster	CY_ARC_12 m ²	0.18 m ³	
CH_ARC_GypsumPlaster	CY_ARC_13 m ²	0.19 m ³	
CH_ARC_GypsumPlaster	CY_ARC_13 m ²	0.14 m ³	

Billing 10 - Plot 131
C Building Information - General

General Information			
street	Stacion	Address	Detonata 1
locality	Stacion	Name of owner	SA Fructosus (Saj) and SA In Jan 2006
inspection	Chetvrtak	Date of inspection	March 2013
symploha data	Adresa 13 in above 10 (one level)	Time of inspection	8:30 am
number	131	Name of inspector	Kyriakos Systems, Elena Apostolova

Building Information			
type of use	residential	Public	
building unit type	residential	Detached	
building year class	1963	1965-1999	1995-2008
number of floors	Two floors	Three floors	
possibility (select at least as required)	orb	South	East
orientation	Southwest	Southwest	Southwest

Life Cycle Assessment for LCA in compliance with EN 15979							
6-Steps	GWP	Ac	CO2e	AP	EP	POCP	ADPE
1.4.1 Construction Materials	9.1014	3.3054	1.1927	4.1923	5.0821	3.781	3.600
4 Transportation to site	3.2813	-	4.0274	1.081	2.089	1.687	4.102
5 Capitalized operational process	4.8913	-	4.0274	3.2813	3.8899	2.989	2.089
LCA End of life	0.001	-	1.4024	1.1923	1.1923	1.4024	1.1923
total	1.8018	3.3054	1.4023	4.0273	4.0812	3.081	3.081

Indicators describing the usage of primary energy and water							
6-Steps	PERSE	PERSEK	PERE	PENSEK	PERE	PERE	PERE
1.4.1 Construction Materials	4.023	4.023	4.023	4.023	4.023	4.023	4.023
4 Transportation to site	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001
5 Construction/Installation process	3.081	3.081	3.081	3.081	3.081	3.081	3.081
LCA End of life	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001
total	4.706	4.706	4.706	4.706	4.706	4.706	4.706

Site Impacts (energy, water, transportation manufacturing)							
6-Steps	GWP	PER	WC	DT	PC	PC	PC
4.1 Transportation of construction materials	4.701	1.199	1.191	1.199	1.194	1.194	1.194

Documents

IFC Manual

BIM Execution Plan & Playbook

EIR for LCA

In an H-BIM context, the parametric modeling process, the basis of any BIM procedure, involves the proper modeling of the heritage building components, which are typically irregular, of variable difference, and complex geometry, in a BIM environment. To simplify the development of BIM modeling, the UP BIM team adopts the modeling process in LOD 200, which according to AIA refers to the relative geometry with generic elements shown in 3D. In parallel, the study and the design of shapes, patterns, or standards for the establishment of collections of parametric objects must be conducted to detail the project according to the survey data with LOD 300.

The next step concerns the construction of a parametric library that contains all architectural elements of the pilot buildings and requires the detailed study of construction techniques of every heritage building, its typology, and relevant historical resources. Moreover, the historical characteristics of historical rules that had applied to its architectural elements, such as ornamentation or window typology, are represented in computational modelling, through specific collections of parametric objects. The generation of a particular family of historical openings should be drafted by using the modelling capacity of the BIM software -Revit. Every parametric object that had been designed by the BIM team will be part of the UP H-BIM library.

The following step of the proposed methodology regards Material management. Material Layer Composition needs adequate consideration in built heritage projects for several reasons. In doing so, the objectives of this phase were to identify the challenges of BIM integration with construction materials' management and their representation. Building material composition has its basis on the data collected by the Existing Conditions Survey and the Conservation State Analysis. Generated in the Existing Conditions Survey the data that were collected and analyzed resulted in a detailed and realistic reconstruction of the exterior and interior facades of the buildings through the creation of orthomosaics. Orthomosaics are not only the main input for the textures of the materials but also create a helpful detailed surface map of the building cracks, for conservation state analysis. Moreover, the data collected by Conservation state analysis provide all the necessary physical characteristics of every construction material, such as the physical and thermal properties, the surface temperature of building elements, ambient temperature, humidity levels etc.

The Conservation State Analysis team employs an integrated procedure for applying IR thermography, and sonic impulse techniques for the on-site examination of damage to heritage buildings, as well as to define the structural and thermal properties of the buildings. This investigation involves different types of buildings and aims to examine the damage mechanisms due to weathering and climate change. The thermal properties of the building materials are also defined. The information concerning the structural aspects of the investigated buildings has been delivered in datasets and is being integrated into the BIM models.

The last part of the present methodology occurs the historical data that the BIM team receives from the Existing Condition survey data controller. A series of project parameters based on the produced metadata schemas document- *UP_WP7_D7.2_002_MetadataSchemas_CyI_280820* and have been imported to Revit (*.rvt template)-Project information section as shared parameters to enrich the model with all the historical data.

The final step of the HBIM implementation is the creation of the H-BIM model, as well as the use of interactive visualization, to visualize and assist in the interpretation of complex information using a cloud-based interactive walkthrough file and VR (*exe files). This feature enables all the stakeholders to work together remotely and assist in reducing errors due to uncoordinated actions. The interactive mapping tool offers advanced functionalities in terms of data visualization in a collaboration environment with multiple functions, including zooming, selecting, hovering, filtering, printing, comparing, etc. 4D simulations as typology color schedules and phasing, and bill of quantities (BOQ), performed in this task to assess the expected performance of the heritage building under/after renovation. After the building model is evaluated and approved by the relevant partners then the 'as-built BIM model will be stored, as an open-source IFC file, published and used as input for the BIM Platform.

3.3. BIM Modeling Strategy

The scope of BIM modeling strategy is the integration on the HBIM models data related to building's existing condition, conservation state analysis, 3D survey, as well as diverse forms of geometric/shape characterization of architectural components (patterns, geometric rules) and ways of archiving unstructured datasets like old drawings, or 'as-built' models. With the intention to identify architecturally valuable buildings, as the overarching goal, the HBIM produced documentation (in the form of templates and guidelines) is about the principal BIM modelling strategies, and archive procedures, as a contribution to systematizing and organizing the dispersed practical instructions, standards, and theoretical studies related to HBIM - *Figure 9 – BIM Modeling Strategy Diagram*.

INPUT

Existing Conditions Information

Conservation state analysis

Existing Conditions Survey

3D Geometrical Reconstruction of Cultural Asset

Families Generation / Classification & Material Composition

Structural and thermal condition integration with NDT

A series of project parameters are imported to Revit -Project information section as shared parameters to enrich the model with all the historical data: Construction, Current conditions, Owner, Original Use, Date, Period, Main material, Finishings, Municipality, Occupation Status, Repository Location, Listing Status etc.

Historical Data Integration

H-BIM Model- ifc file

2D drawings

4D typology

5D -BOQ

Life-Cycle Assessment for Level(s) in compliance with EN 15978							
Result category	Global warming potential	Biogenic carbon storage	Other carbon storage	Acidification potential	Eutrophication potential	Formation of ozone layer depletion	Abiotic depletion (ADP, element) for non fossil resources
	kg CO ₂ e	kg CO ₂ e	kg CO ₂ e	kg SO ₂ e	kg PO ₄ e	kg CFC11e	kg Sb ₂ e
A1-A3 Construction in use	1,183	1,5484	1,28-3	3,9962	3,9261	3,1881	8,180
A4 Construction in use process	3,283			6,296-4	1,4283	3,180	2,008-1
B1 Use Phase	6,9983	9,588-3	2,463	2,760	2,3650	1,030	
B3 Repair and replacement	0E0	0E0	0E0	0E0	0E0	0E0	0E0
B4 B5 Material replacement and refurbishment	0E0	0E0	0E0	0E0	0E0	0E0	0E0
B6 Energy use							
B7 Water use							
C1-C4 Total of life cycle	1,5483	1,5484	1,5484	1,5483	1,5483	1,5483	1,5483
Total	1,2483	1,5484	1,5484	4,9962	4,9761	3,681	3,2761

6D -LCA

H-BIM – Digital twin

OUTPUT

Information Delivery Plan

All stages described in the present document are part of the H-BIM-based design asset strategy that was formulated based on international standards, good practices and experimental outcomes. According to the description of all the stages, all building elements must be modelled within the given geometrical and alphanumeric field specifications, in addition to their precise quantity, size, shape, location, material, and orientation. The level of geometrical detail and naming convention should also comply with the international LOD 350 requirements. All H-BIM models also contains colour schedules for annotating the heritage information, BOQ of all the materials used and enables the visualization of the BIM model components and building semantics efficiently. All the data described above must be exported and organised based on the diagram below. Doing so will link data according to existing knowledge graphs and formal vocabularies of definitions of the terms used in the documentation of built heritage. Moreover, this document presents an informational model of heritage buildings that can be used for conservation and retrofitting applications. By extend, the UP BIM methodology designates the IFC model structures as the final digital format of the models uploaded in the online platform, for promoting Open BIM standards and software compatibility.

For making the H-BIM models compatible with energy simulation analyses, the current document provides suggestions and techniques on how the energy requirement data could be integrated to the H-BIM models (BIM 6D). The document also offers BIM modelling practices on how to minimise the geometrical conversion inconsistencies when converting the detailed three-dimensional BIM model to the three-dimensional planar surface energy model. The provided guides are based on the gbXML exchange schema using the 'Revit spaces' export method, capable of securing a smoother interoperability between Revit and energy simulation software that are combatable importers of energy models in gbXML file format.

02_hBIM

Existing Conditions Survey

3D Geometrical Reconstruction

2D Drawings

Materials

hBIM Library

ifc

Sheet list

Bill Of Quantities(BOQ)

Material: Name	Type	Material: Area	Material: Volume
20_ARC_GypsumMarblesTiles	UP_ARC_Ceiling_Cracking	7.54	0.17
20_ARC_GypsumMarblesTiles	UP_ARC_Ceiling_Cracking	4.91	0.27
		12.46	0.43
20_ARC_Timber	UP_ARC_Ceiling_Timber	35.13	0.3
20_ARC_Timber	UP_ARC_Ceiling_Timber	9.39	0.3
20_ARC_Timber	UP_ARC_Ceiling_Timber	10.35	0.31
20_ARC_Timber	UP_ARC_Ceiling_Timber	30	0.3
20_ARC_Timber	UP_ARC_Ceiling_Timber	6.3	0.27
20_ARC_Timber	UP_ARC_Ceiling_Timber	35.21	0.31
20_ARC_Timber	UP_ARC_Ceiling_Timber	9.77	0.29
20_ARC_Timber	UP_ARC_Ceiling_Timber	9.04	0.27
20_ARC_Timber	UP_ARC_Ceiling_Timber	35.13	0.3
20_ARC_Timber	UP_ARC_Ceiling_Timber	35.13	0.3
20_ARC_Timber	UP_ARC_Ceiling_Timber	35.13	0.3
20_ARC_Timber	UP_ARC_Ceiling_Timber	35.13	0.3
20_ARC_Timber	UP_ARC_Ceiling_Timber	35.13	0.3
20_ARC_Timber	UP_ARC_Ceiling_Timber	35.13	0.3
20_ARC_Timber	UP_ARC_Ceiling_Timber	35.53	1.1
20_ARC_Timber	UP_ARC_Ceiling_Timber	185.97	5.28

Sheet Number	Sheet Name	Drawn By	Designed By	Approved By
STR21.703.3	3rd Historical Phase	WPF-CH	CH	
STR21.703.4	Existing Conditions Survey	WPA-CH	CH	
STR21.704.1	Sections	WPF-CH	CH	
STR21.703.1	3rd Historical Phase	WPF-CH	CH	
STR21.703.1	3D Geometrical Reconstruction	WPF-CH	CH	
STR21.703.2	Conservation state analysis	WPF-CH	CH	
STR21.703.3	Existing Conditions Survey	WPA-CH	CH	
STR21.703.3	Existing Conditions Information	WPA-CH	CH	
STR21.703.2	3D Geometrical Reconstruction	WPF-CH	CH	
STR21.703.2	3D Geometrical Reconstruction	WPF-CH	CH	
STR21.703.2	3D Geometrical Reconstruction	WPF-CH	CH	
STR21.704.2	2nd Historical Phase	WPF-CH	CH	
STR21.704.2	Elevations	WPF-CH	CH	
STR21.705.1	Structural and thermal condition with NDT	WPF-CH	CH	
STR21.705.1	Structural and thermal condition with NDT	WPF-CH	CH	
STR21.704.5	Phasing	WPF-CH	CH	
STR21.704.5	BOQ	WPF-CH	CH	
STR21.704.6	BOQ	WPF-CH	CH	
STR21.704.6	3rd Historical Phase	WPF-CH	CH	
STR21.704.3	General Views	WPF-CH	CH	
STR21.704.4	Window and Door Schedule	WPF-CH	CH	
STR21.704.7	BOQ	WPF-CH	CH	
STR21.705.2	Structural and thermal condition with NDT	WPF-CH	CH	

03_LCA

LCA Report

Building 13 - Plot 411		3.X Building Information - General		3.X.1 LCA-EPD Assessment for Embodied Carbon Footprint		3.X.1 LCA-EPD Assessment for Embodied Carbon Footprint	
Building Name	Building 13 - Plot 411	Address	1300-1310	EPD Standard	EN 15804	EPD Standard	EN 15804
Client	Client	Project Name	Project Name	EPD Version	3.1	EPD Version	3.1
Project Manager	Project Manager	Project Location	Project Location	EPD Scope	Product	EPD Scope	Product
Project Start	Project Start	Project End	Project End	EPD Impact	Global Warming Potential (CO2e)	EPD Impact	Global Warming Potential (CO2e)
Project Status	Project Status	Project Type	Project Type	EPD Emissions	Embodied Carbon Footprint (kg CO2e/m²)	EPD Emissions	Embodied Carbon Footprint (kg CO2e/m²)
Project Description	Project Description	Project Details	Project Details	EPD Results	Embodied Carbon Footprint (kg CO2e/m²)	EPD Results	Embodied Carbon Footprint (kg CO2e/m²)
Project Objectives	Project Objectives	Project Goals	Project Goals	EPD Summary	Embodied Carbon Footprint (kg CO2e/m²)	EPD Summary	Embodied Carbon Footprint (kg CO2e/m²)
Project Risks	Project Risks	Project Challenges	Project Challenges	EPD Conclusions	Embodied Carbon Footprint (kg CO2e/m²)	EPD Conclusions	Embodied Carbon Footprint (kg CO2e/m²)
Project Opportunities	Project Opportunities	Project Recommendations	Project Recommendations	EPD Recommendations	Embodied Carbon Footprint (kg CO2e/m²)	EPD Recommendations	Embodied Carbon Footprint (kg CO2e/m²)
Project Next Steps	Project Next Steps	Project Contact Information	Project Contact Information	EPD Disclaimer	Embodied Carbon Footprint (kg CO2e/m²)	EPD Disclaimer	Embodied Carbon Footprint (kg CO2e/m²)

05 Interactive Visualization

360 Renderings

Renderings

*exe file

WebStand Alone

4.2 BIM QA/QC

Model validation is to be completed by the BIM Team before exchanging information with rest stakeholders. In addition, systematic BIM checks should be performed by the Project BIM team at key stages.

Checks	Definitions	Responsible Party	Software Program	Frequency
VISUAL CHECK	Ensure there are no unintended model components and the design intent have been followed.	UP BIM Team	Revit	Weekly
STANDARDS CHECK	Ensure that the BIM and AEC CADD Standards have been followed (fonts, dimensions, line styles, levels/layers, etc.)	UP BIM Team	Revit	Weekly
MODEL INTEGRITY CHECKS	QC validation process used to ensure that the Project Facility Data set has no-undefined, incorrectly defined or duplicated elements and the reporting process on non-compliant elements and corrective action plans	UP BIM Team	Revit	Weekly
NAMING CHECKS	Model Check to ensure correct Nomenclature is enforced for all elements (Families/ Types) as described in related document	UP BIM Team	Revit	Weekly

- All rooms shall be modelled using the Room tool in Revit. The use of filled regions/text to identify a room is prohibited.
- All rooms must be enclosed properly with bounding.
- All areas shall be modelled using the Area tool in Revit. The use of filled regions/text to identify an area is prohibited.
- All Drawings generated must be created in Revit. If the Designer wishes to use AutoCAD for some of the details, those details must be linked to a view inside the Revit Model(s) and placed on a sheet in Revit. The Designer must create an AutoCAD file for each detail. Each AutoCAD File will be linked to a Drafting View within Revit.
- All schedules shown on the Sheets must be derived from elements in the Revit Model(s).

- All Revit family names and types in the models must match the actual geometry.
- Only one building is to be modelled inside of each file.
- All naming conventions not specifically defined in this document must remain consistent for the duration of the project, including punctuation and capitalization.
- Phases must be coordinated with the architect at project inception.
- Structural walls are to extend floor to floor and not full height.
- Elements must be modeled using the correct categories. When modeling in-place families, the correct category must be assigned.
- All wall openings shall be generic model openings. This is a new family and decreases the need for room separation lines (which then cause errors when the walls move).
- When making new sheets for any phase, the sheet should be made to a level to be able to be printed at a moment's notice. An empty placeholder sheet is not advisable.
- Model elements are to be associated to the proper level.
- If individual model files exceed 250MB it is advisable to consider model segregation.

Planning and Documentation

5.1 LOD Requirements

The following measures and activities will be followed and adhered to by the BIM team until the handing-over process:

- 1- The BIM implementation guidelines, specifications, workflows, Common Data Environment, Collaboration workflows, clash detection/resolution, construction BIM uses-cases, Level of details and level of information will be strictly followed and read from BIM Execution Plan and BIM Implementation Documents.
- 2- International regulations and standards such as ISO19650 and the BIM forum definition for LOD will be followed.
- 3- Models will be fed progressively with the information (attributes, properties, and documents) described in BIM methodology diagrams.
- 4- LOD350 definition for this project has been adopted.

5.2 Collaboration-CDE

A Common Data Environment has been set up by the *EIR for BIM* at the design stage in the BIM Platform.

Standard Methods and Procedures

6.1 Folder structure

In the Project Files folder and subfolders of the CDE, teams will upload all data relevant to the project to enhance coordination and communication between the different teams. The Sharing functionality of the BIM platform will be used for all involved parties to be notified when a relevant piece of information (Revit Models, Drawings, Documents etc.) is uploaded.

6.2 Document Name Convention

The BIM Team will preserve and use the same Document Name Convention system that has been specified by the UP Team on the project- *Name Convention* document.

6.3 Drawing and Model Naming Convention

The BIM Team will preserve and use the same Drawing and Model Naming Convention system that has been specified by the UP team on the project *Name Convention* document.